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Multipath Communication for Cloud Security

Tariqul Islam¹, Md. Mahfujur Rahman²

Daffodil International University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

¹tariqul15-2250@diu.edu.bd, ²mrrajuiit@gmail.com

Abstract. This paper aims at providing complete solutions to address private communication from the client to cloud, i.e., to transfer data over channels without exposing its content. The idea is that cloud infrastructures, despite all the advantages, raise privacy and data integrity issues that are not satisfactorily addressed by existing technologies. Revelations made by former NSA contractor Edward Snowden show that Internet traffic is not routed through the physically most direct path, but through the path considered the “cheapest”, suggesting that this may be used to intercept on traffic. To address these issues, this paper aims to provide a mechanism to improve confidentiality in communications by splitting packet flows (each flow) into different physical paths. This makes snooping attacks less effective. The document will consider the provisioning of multi-path TCP through multi-path routes. In practice, multi-path communication requires making IP packets follow different routes, which is not possible at the network level using the standard Internet routing. Mechanisms will be provided to select paths based on diversity, measured in the number of physical paths used, and trust, measured in geographic location and number of packets dropped.

Keywords: Multi-path Routing, Cloud Security, Communication Confidentiality, Eaves dropping, Deep Learning

1 Introduction

Cloud systems are increasingly used for data sharing and storing between devices connection to the Internet, whether it is for personal or business use. They offer a reliable data storage alternative with the advantages of removing the concern of hardware maintenance and treatment and having the information accessible in any device that is connected to the Internet. In the case of entities where confidentiality is critical this problem is decisive. In general, implementing cryptographic systems provides the security needed to keep the information confidential, but certain devices may be unable to implement such systems. This inability is a problem that is already addressed in wireless mesh networks since this type of network is built upon devices that are not capable of implementing any kind of cryptographic system. Recent facts also show that is possible to break these systems in certain conditions. Adrian et al. [1] investigated a new flaw in the Diffie-Hellman key exchange that manages to downgrade a TLS connection for a specified 512-bit group.

Our research aims to address the problem of providing a new level of security to communications, assuming cryptographic mechanisms are not enough to defend against eavesdropping attacks. The goal is to provide a system where all data is

transferred among several paths over the Internet without requiring the need for changes in its structure. Path selection should be as physically disjoint as possible, path selection should be randomized according to lower and upper bounds of geographical region, the security of communication should always take precedence over performance, but a minimal level performance must be acceptable. This approach will use the MPTCP protocol to distribute packets among channels, therefore it is assumed there will be no problems with packet bursts and reordering in case of unordered delivery. It also assumes that the network nodes chosen in the path selection can redirect the packets to the destination. The result will be the implementation and testing of a functional framework that follows the above-mentioned requirements and should provide the expected level of security.

2 Related work

When talking about path diversity, the goal that the majority of studies tend to achieve is resilience and performance, either on the Internet itself or on WSN. However, it is significant to notice that multipath routing brings advantages in the security of communications. Some studies have been made in the sense of implementing diversity of channels with an emphasis on security. The most generic motivations to study it are the performance and robustness benefits. Selecting multiple paths for reaching one destination and using an Intelligent balancing algorithm is how a connection can survive individual path failures and maximize the use of bandwidth in each channel. Path diversity is the quality that defines and measures the use of multiple routes to reach a destination, whether they are physical or virtual. When there is path diversity, instead of using a single path from a source to a destination, it is possible to split the traffic among several paths and nodes before reaching the destination. In other words, it consists of applying multi-path routing to communications. It is important to measure path diversity according to the number of physical paths used, i.e., the level of physical layer disjoint topology. For example, if only a single physical path is used, but it contains two or more virtual paths, in the case where the physical path is being eavesdropped on, no security is added to the communication. In general, maximum amount of physical paths according to the number of virtual paths used will lead to more efficient and secure communication. In fact, in a good scenario, dividing the traffic over two or three extra physical paths is enough for reacting to path failures, balancing the communication load, and improving security. To avoid congested paths, router failures, and adversary packet dropping attacks, it is necessary to have a system that can quickly switch paths and distribute information [2].

Path failure correlations can also cause many paths to fail, emphasizing the need to have intelligent path selection. In the case of not choosing completely physically disjoint paths, congestion or failure of a physical path or router will highly affect the availability and performance of connections [3]. Several approaches have been studied to introduce diversity in communications. Even though it is highly believed that most approaches, such as overlay routing, multi-homing, and multi-path TCP, provide significant benefits, their effectiveness depends on the level of path diversity between two

end-points at the physical layer. Han et al. [3] present a study proving that in many cases implementing either multi-homing or overlay networks can have a bad outcome in communications. Due to the lack of physically disjoint paths in some cases, it is possible that implementing path diversity might bring performance inefficiency. This paper needs to measure path diversity in communication. It will not only avoid several resilience problems but also provide a more versatile path selection mechanism. These approaches and others are explained in the next section, addressing the issues that arise when trying to achieve adequate levels of path diversity.

2.1 Multi-homing

Multi-homing is one approach of achieving path diversity. Simply said, having a customer network connected to two or more Internets is what this concept entails. ISPs (Internet Service Providers) are depicted in Figure 1. the key advantages of this approach are its resilience and performance. Different providers give different degrees of performance to different portions of the network, therefore selecting the "correct" provider will result in an increase in performance [4]. Akella et al. [5] assess the utilization of multi-homing in data centers and organizations, using HRTT as a measurement unit. These studies [4] conclude that simply using two providers improves performance by at least 25%, and that improvements beyond four providers are negligible. The same authors [4] conducted a similar but more in-depth k-homing investigation, evaluating the performance of tiny (10 KB) and medium-sized (1 MB) file transfers based on RTT and throughput. In general, all multi-homing studies come to the same conclusion: using two or three providers improves performance by 15-25 percent.

Fig. 1. Example of a multi-homing connection.

The Stream Control Transmission Protocol (SCTP) is an example of a transport protocol that natively supports multi-homing. This protocol with the addition of the Concurrent Multipath Transfer (CMT) [6] extension allows not only to connect to different destination addresses but also through and different interfaces. Another option to implement multi-homing is the MONET web proxy system [7] that aims to improve client access availability specifically on websites. To do so, each address bound by the DNS name in a replicated site is related to a different server machine or the Internet path.

According to the evaluation made on [7], this approach has proven to be very good to mask and recover from path failures compared to the traditional DNS queries with low time to live (TTL) that force the client to refresh the mapping. In theory, this methodology is full of advantages and presents a very good choice to achieve path diversity. However, multi-homing not always provide the desired level of diversity [8]. Based on the test made in [8], 80% of 80,000 connections to the same destination using different providers overlap. This happens due to the lack of control from each hop to the next one and the architecture of the Internet's core, to which no solution has been found yet unless there is a massive Internet restructuring.

2.2 Overlay Routing

Overlay routing is a mechanism that allows the creation of a virtual network built on top of an existing network architecture that isn't changed. An overlay link is created between two nodes making them virtually connected, independently of the physical paths that it is crossing in the underlying network. A PTP network is an overlay network, since each peer connects to another peer using the Internet. A level of abstraction is added to the underlying physical topology. At the physical level, the packets travel in the actual physical structures that contain this virtual network. An indirect virtual path is composed of several physical devices, however, the abstraction created by the overlay network allows it to be treated as an end-to-end link. Resilience is the major advantage brought by this ability to send packets through indirect virtual paths. It allows fast path failure recovery and congestion control. An example is shown below in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Example of an overlay network.

Several proposals exist for overlay routing mechanisms that aim to maximize the resilience of communications. Andersen et al. present RON (Resilient Overlay Network) [9], an application-layer overlay network on top of the Internet. It has many nodes deployed over the Internet that form an application-layer overlay network. Each node periodically probes its links to other nodes so that it can quickly detect path failures and monitor the quality of the connection. The main advantage of this architecture is the ability to recover from path failures within seconds, which is a major benefit compared to current wide-area routing protocols like Border Gateway Protocol. The fact that RON is small-sized compared to the Internet (a net constituted by 50 or

60 nodes is usually appropriate) allows the protocol to keep information of latency, packet loss, and throughput of a link. The architecture proved to be able to recover from more than 60% of the outages in an average time of 18 seconds. Amir and Danilov [10] propose a reliable hop-by-hop overlay that recovers from losses only on the overlay hop that caused the outage, enabling a fast recovery. To do so each link must have its own set of acknowledgments of packets so that it is possible to know exactly where the packet failed to send. Moreover, to increase the congestion window and deal with packet bursts, nodes also implement buffers. Processing in intermediate nodes is required to deploy this protocol. Another proposal is the one presented by Snoeren et al. [11] which is a mesh-based content routing using XML. Its architecture is based on an overlay network that transports XML streams. Each client or device that joins the network sends a query informing which types of packets they are available to send and the overlay network re-arranges itself to deliver the desired packets. The advantages of this method are: It allows the network to correctly interpret client data, The protocol allows the calculation of which packets are going to be processed together, aiding network scheduling; and XML is an easy language to parse and many tools exist for it, making it easy to receive and send queries among clients or devices.

2.3 Topology-Aware Overlay Routing

Topology-Aware Overlay Routing is an approach that aims to select the overlay links and nodes based on their topological dis-jointness to maximize the path diversity. Han et al. [12] provide a topology-aware framework for overlay networks that aims to maximize physical independence without demoting performance. The key aspect is to select a subset of routers and ISPs that present a good level of topological diversity and performance. To do so, it is necessary to measure routers regarding two metrics from a set of sources to destinations: - Router path diversity: measured based on the number of shared routers between overlay paths and physical direct paths; - Router latency: defined by the difference of RTT using the overlay layer and using the physical most direct path. The nodes between a source and destination node can be set either statically or dynamically to get an extensive evaluation. Choosing routers dynamically has been shown to provide a high level of diversity and provides better latency than direct physical paths. Once all routers are rated by their neighbors it is necessary to know which ISPs contain routers that are worth using, but the comparison is not straight-forward. From each ISP, the k most diverse routers are chosen and each ISP has evaluated fork nodes (where k varies from one to ten), according to the evaluation methodology stated above. In general, studying each ISP for each possibility of k provided the same results for the different ISPs. After the evaluation for a single ISP is made, there is a need to study the path diversity gain from increasing the number of ISPs. For example, for two ISPs, all the possible combinations of a pair of ISPs should be studied. Based on the author's experiments, the most significant gain in what matters to physical diversity is changing from one to two ISPs. On the other hand, regarding latency, using only one ISP proved to perform as well as deploying the network in all ten ISPs used in the experiment. The author's final evaluation shows that it is possible to recover up to 87% of path outages with the correct node selection which is a better value compared to the ones obtained before.

2.4 Single-hop vs. Multi-hop Overlay Routing

Another decision to have into account is the number of hops used in each path, i.e., single-hop vs. multi-hop paths. RON is an example of a protocol that uses a complex multi-hop system, yet the experimental studies made in [9] showed that most outages were avoided by using a single node. For the topological aware framework, the authors also studied the performance achieved on a direct physical path, a single-hop path, and a multi-hop path [12]. The metric used for comparison is the RTT, which is a direct physical path that is easy to acquire. For a single-hop, it needed to add the RTT from the source to the chosen hop and that same hop to the destination. In the last case, where multiple hops are used, the best scenario is assumed when: the source chooses the best entry node with the least overlapping routers; the best “exit” node to destination is also always selected; the path between the entry and exit nodes do not present any overlapping. According to the results presented, single-hop overlay paths suffice in what matters to path diversity and latency. Gummadi et al. [13] also present a single-hop source routing (SOSR) that aims to recover from path failures using a single hop from the source. Hops are chosen based on a random-4 policy, which chooses four random hops next to the source and only then redirects packets through an indirect path. To arrive at the number 4 for the policy, the authors made a random-k study and the results revealed that this is the best value regarding the over-head and amount of path failures recovery. This protocol can recover from 56% of network failures while adding low overhead and providing good scalability. Table 1 shows an analysis of overlay routing protocols in terms of physical topology and fault recovery.

Table 1. Comparison of overlay routing protocols.

Overlay Routing Protocols	Topologically disjoint	Fault-recovery
Mesh-based XML	7	-
RON	7	60%
SOSR	7	56%
Topological Aware Framework	3	87%

2.5 Multi-path TCP

Multi-path TCP (MPTCP), a modification of the TCP protocol that allows the use of several IP addresses and interfaces while connecting between endpoints [14, 15], is a third way to create path redundancy and diversity. The protocol determines which paths are accessible, establishes a connection, and divides traffic between them. It has the same programming interface as TCP, but the data is split into many sub-flows. In the conventional TCP protocol, the options field is populated with MPTCP data structures to keep track of all packet status (sent/failed) via the various sub-flows. Since this protocol is implemented over multi-homing or overlay networks, the main advantage is, as mentioned before, the resilience of communication.

Path Discovery: To implement MPTCP, it is important to maximize the throughput to the sum of all available channels. Therefore, the path discovery algorithm must not only choose the paths with most efficiency and lower load, but also maximize the number of paths used, i.e, not as many as possible, but the number of paths that achieve the

highest performance of the data transfer. Several algorithms were implemented [16] that have been shown to achieve the same amount of distinct routes for each one:

Flood Method: Since routers can only know their direct neighbors, the method floods the neighborhood information from the emission node to the destination node with the aid of Discovery Packets. These packets contain the Flood Time To Live, a list of addresses already visited. Based on that weight and number of hops visited, the routes are chosen on the destination node.

Fig. 3. Example of path discovery from N1 to N4 using the flood method.

The modified version of k-Dijkstra's Algorithm: It is based on the original shortest path of Dijkstra's algorithm, but the initial weights are the real topology. Other than changing the weight of the link as the original algorithm does, a constant that represents the maximum weight between two nodes is added to the links. With this feature, the probability of having a link appearing twice in the calculation of new shortest paths is low.

The modified version of Bellman-Ford's Algorithm: Bellman-Ford's algorithm is applied to all direct neighbors of the emission node where the destination is the destination node. The algorithm is also applied to all direct neighbors of the destination node where the destination is the emission node. Posteriorly, all routes are merged generating new ones and the shortest path is calculated from those.

Congestion Control: The implementation of this protocol also comes with the need of having a good congestion control algorithm. It is only worth using MPTCP if a good congestion control system is used. In general, the key to implementing a good congestion control scheme is to calculate a congestion control window. For example, one solution is to have a connection with several sub-flows where each sub-flow has an algorithm that calculates the congestion window based RTT on that same sub-flow. Deeper mathematical solutions have also been studied for the congestion window calculation, such as the one presented in that studies the stability of the congestion control loop based on the Nyquist Condition.

The mechanisms mentioned above and the algorithms used to allow the users to use the best paths available are optimal in static settings. Though they might have some problems, such as the failure of detecting free capacity due to not probing sufficiently paths with high loss probability, randomly flipping packets through channels if there are multiple good channels, users with MPTCP will reduce the throughput of others

with regular TCP, etc. These cases have already been studied and Khalili et al. [17] present an algorithm that solves them, by correctly dividing the throughput between clients with MPTCP and TCP and making the RTT a characteristic with more importance on the channel decision. All three mechanisms presented in this section are related. Multi-homing provides a greater amount of nodes to select when creating an overlay network, therefore allowing to have a greater level of path diversity. Once the overlay network is created, MPTCP is applied between the endpoints to distribute the data. Architecture proposed, all three mechanisms are used. It is also important to notice that the overlay network will be topologically aware and will also consist of several single overlay hop links, i.e. when creating an overlay link it is only necessary that the communication goes through one overlay node.

2.6 Multi-path Routing for Security

So far the implementation of path diversity has been studied to increase the availability, resilience, and reliability of networks. However, the aim of our research is the use of several paths to increase the security of connections. Assuming the attacker manages to spy on a single end-to-end channel, the communication is vulnerable to eavesdropping among many other types of attack. Using multiple channels jeopardizes only part of the information. Studying multi-path routing protocols with an emphasis on security might be the key to achieving higher levels of security on the Internet [18]. For critical infrastructures (military, health care, government, etc.) a trade-off between performance and security must be taken into account where the second might need to be privileged [19]. Several protocols presented below apply multi-path routing with a focus on security. Most of them accomplish the objective based on node selection according to their rate on a certain characteristic. In general, each node has a different trust level and decides which neighbor is the next hop based on their trust level. This depends on different characteristics, such as geographic location, packets forwarded, response time, among others. Other characteristics might condition the next-hop decision, however, trust is the most used condition so far. It is important to notice that most of the studies were made for wireless networks that can't handle other security measures. The capability of having, for example, a node with a geographic locator device is possible in wireless sensor nodes but can be difficult when using wired devices [20]. These situations have not yet been given enough attention in wired networks due to the existence of cryptography mechanisms in most WAN devices. Since wireless sensors are unable to implement these mechanisms, it is necessary to find different methods to obtain security, namely multi-path communication. Security is now the goal of implementing multi-path routing and trust is the metric used in nodes selection. As mentioned above, it is important to measure trust. Different authors present several options to measure it for each node of the network.

3 Architecture

After efforts to apply multi-path routing over the Internet mentioned in the previous section, it is possible to realize that none of them completely achieves all the goals of this project by itself. The next subsections present the components and behavior of the proposed architecture.

3.1 Component Structure

To provide the desired confidentiality, assuming there is no cryptography and the number of physical paths may be conditioned, the following architecture is proposed at the application level. The components structured are as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Component's structure of the framework.

API: Connects the framework for the cloud application itself, working as a bridge of data that will trigger the discovery and selection of the overlay network on the part of the Path Discovery Handler;

Path Discovery Handler: Once the API transmits a signal that is ready to send data, this component is in charge of discovering the list of network nodes upon which it is possible to build the overlay network. Once the list is made it is necessary to rate the trust at each node. According to the previous rate, this component also decides which nodes will support the overlay links in the network according to the level of path diversity achieved by a certain selection.

Packet Handler: This component is responsible for splitting the data given by the API among the links created by the Path Discovery Handler and, using the MPTCP

protocol, sending the data to the nodes previously selected. It must also append the information of the destination so that the nodes know to where they should redirect the packets;

Network Coding Handler: In the case, the Path Discovery Handler does not provide enough links, the Packet Handler will trigger this component. Linear network coding is applied to the packets that will be later decoded by the destination. This component is also responsible for generating the packets that contain the coefficients for network coding after Shamir's secret sharing algorithm is applied;

Node: Represents a virtual list of the network nodes' information, containing the values for trust, geographic location, recorded packets dropped, recorded packets received, and response time since the information was requested by the Path Discovery Handler.

3.2 Component Structure

The behavior of the system consists mainly of two steps when transmitting information between two end-points: the path 'discovery and selection' phase and the 'transmission' phase. In the first phase, the system will flood the nodes that can compose the network, i.e., the nodes that can process packets sent by the source and redirect them to the destination. The packets are sent to neighbors of the source, and these neighbors will posteriorly send to their neighbors and so on, as shown in Fig. 5. The algorithm will only accept, however, the nodes that are over a constant lower bound and upper bound of depth. The lower bound is used to provide the physical disjointness, nodes further away from the source are more likely to be physical disjoint than closer ones. The upper bound allows the communication to be kept inside the desired range. For example, if a European company wants to keep its information inside Europe, this is possible due to this upper bound. The trust-based topology-aware algorithm also has two phases of calculation. One that guarantees a node selection based on their trust and afterward another that guarantees path diversity. In the first phase, each node's trust t is measured according to their geographic location, recorded packets dropped PD , recorded packets received pr , and response time rt . If no packets were recorded and hence dropped until the node's discovery, their values will be set to one so that the node is not punished during the selection. Once the information is normalized, it is finally possible to rate the trust. Since the response time can vary due to the distance to the source it will be set to either zero, if it overcomes a constant ct that defines the maximum acceptable RTT, or one, if it is acceptable, as shown in the function below.

$$rt = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } rt < ct \\ 0, & \text{if } rt \geq ct \end{cases}$$

This constant ct exists because the objective is not to achieve the highest performance but to achieve an acceptable one while providing the level of security desired. Afterward, the algorithm calculates the percentage of packets forwarded on each node so that it is possible to know which nodes should the system rely on. It is finally possible to retrieve the trust level by multiplying that percentage by the response time:

$$t = \frac{Pd}{Pr} * rt$$

Once the packets are ordered by their trust level, the second phase starts. The nodes are selected having into account the path-diversity achieved. Before the selection starts, any geographic duplicate is deleted, prevailing the node with higher trust. When there are other restrictions, like the European company example, any node outside some pre-set boundaries is also removed. Only then, as expected, the node with a higher trust level is selected (when there is more than one it is randomized) and posterior nodes are selected the same way until it reaches the limit set by a value that is defined according to the amount of data to be sent. The nodes must keep a distance from the nodes previously selected. If a node proves to be close to another then it is quite likely that a part of their path is physically the same, therefore, on each step of the node selection it is necessary to measure the path diversity d achieved. This value will contain the lower distance between two nodes in a finite set of nodes and each node can only be used if that value is over a certain constant.

Once the overlay links are set and the route established it is time to decide if the packets are going to be coded or not. In any case, having two channels is the minimum required to have a multi-path routing protocol and enough to apply network coding. However, it is only possible to have a more accurate value after testing. When choosing this value it is important to notice the performance and security of applying network coding to a higher number of channels. Security should always prevail while there is an acceptable level of performance. There is also the problem of not knowing which type of network coding to use in the source and destination. The proposal is to use linear network coding with a shared secret set of coefficients. Since only the end-point nodes should have the power to completely encode and decode the packets, it is important to keep this set secret. To do so, Shamir's secret sharing algorithm is used. In this case, a polynomial function will be created with the number of shares necessary to retrieve the secret set same to the amount of total shares. If only three channels are available the function should be parabolic so that all shares are required when decrypting.

Fig. 6. Example of sending four packets using different channels, ISPs, and applying network coding. The multi-homing section is only used to represent that different nodes might belong to different ISPs, they do not work as a hop. The watermarked nodes are still part of communication, however, the system only forces the message to be sent over the non-watermarked nodes. The destination retrieves packet p4 by applying a decoding function on packets p3 and p3+p4.

Finally, all the packets are sent to the network. It should be considered that a path can fail in the meantime. Therefore, the Path Discovery Component should provide $k+r$ paths where k represents the expected k links for a normal function of the communication and r represents the links that the Packet Handler will use to recover from failures on the previous ones. If it is not possible to provide this extra value, then the rest of the data should be split among the available channels. As shown in Fig. 6, a single overlay hop is used which means that the application forces the packets to pass through a specific node. To reach it is necessary to go through other nodes.

4 Evaluation

The first step to evaluate this proposal is to select a platform composed of enough nodes so that the tests can be executed. The most reliable option for this is to use PlanetLab, which is a global research network composed of over a thousand nodes that supports the development of network services. The evaluation procedure will focus on two aspects: security and performance. Security is the main goal of this research and, therefore, will be the primary focus. Although, it is important to test the performance of the system so that it is possible to understand if it is deployable in real-world applications. The security tests will mainly consist of evaluating the ability to keep confidentiality on data transmitted in clear and evaluating the ability to circumvent the lack of communication channels. Regarding confidentiality, the appropriate methodology to test is to do a k -testing where k represents the number of channels in a total t that is spied by an untrusted third party, as shown below

$$k = \{1, \dots, t - 1\}$$

The maximum value of k is $t - 1$, If an attacker can spy on all channels, then it is assumed that all information is intercepted and, therefore, in that scenario, this system adds no security. On each iteration of the test, the metrics that will grade the effectiveness of maintaining confidentiality are the percentage of information jeopardized and the percentage that can be regenerated into noncorrupt and reliable data. On the performance aspect, it is important to test the optimized value of total channels used for a specified amount of data. Therefore, it is appropriate to apply another iterative test where the complete time of data transfer is evaluated for small, medium, and large-size files. For example, when transferring a small 10kB file, two to five channels are tested. To measure it, the total of adding time of path selection and data transfer is the appropriate definition for the metric. The previous tests are made without applying network

coding, however, it is also necessary to test the protocol when this mechanism is used. Regarding the confidentiality of communication, the same methodology as before will be applied to lower values of total channels used in communication now applying network coding. This test will have another component when trying to regenerate the intercepted data since it is also necessary to test if an attacker can retrieve the original packets by decoding coded packets. Regarding the performance, the same methodology will be again applied to the same values, but when applying network coding. Therefore, the metric used will consist of the total time of selecting paths, encoding packets, sending data, and decoding packets. Once both sections of testing are done - performance and security - it is necessary to combine them, so that it is possible to know what is the most adequate value that will maximize the confidentiality of communications and provide a decent performance of communication. These tests will prove if it is indeed possible to create a protocol that manages to defend itself from “selective forward” and “denial of service”, which are indirectly correlated to the confidentiality of communications, and provide another layer of security against the eavesdropping attacks that directly fight the confidentiality.

5 Conclusion

This research analyzed several methodologies that aim to distribute the communications through several channels, whether it is applied in wireless mesh networks or at the Internet itself. Multi-homing and overlay routing are currently the most used approaches to reach this goal, however, they are mainly focused on performance and failure recovery. Therefore, a different approach was also studied: the ability to implement multi-path routing with a focus on security, most specifically in confidentiality. There are certainly many types of attacks that influence the confidentiality of communications directly or indirectly, but, in the scope of this research, it was considered that the attacks that mostly affect confidentiality are “eavesdropping” or “denial of service” related. Breaking the cryptography of a channel and spying on the information that circulates on it is the attack that most directly compromises the confidentiality of the communication. In general, the idea to fight this is to distribute the communication among several channels so that only part of the information is compromised. However, this methodology is susceptible to new types of attacks. “Selective forwarding” or “black-hole” are two types of attacks that aim to disable certain network nodes, forcing the communication to go through the nodes desired by the attacker. In this sense, the goal of this research is to provide and evaluate a mechanism, implemented at the application level, that aims at mitigating both of these threats. By distributing communication among several channels, using the methodologies previously stated, and applying network coding when the available channels are not enough, it is possible to improve the resistance to threats that aim to intercept communications.

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